

ALL OPPORTUNITIES - FOR NATURE, TO PROTECT NATURE

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Allah has given us human beings great blessings for us to enjoy. The most valuable of these blessings is nature. Nature is a land of miracles created by God, the world of plants, which has a place for thousands of animals, plants and other living beings. In Nasiruddin Rabguzi's "Kissasi Rabguzi" it is written as follows: "Allah the Almighty created the whole world in six days. (Verse) "Verily, We created the heavens, the earth and everything in the middle of the document in six days." -shared the fortunes, on Thursday he created heaven, hell, angels of mercy and torment, angels, on Friday he created Adam, on Saturday he did not create anything. "Even if I am able, I will not come in a hurry." The Messenger of God said: "Hurry is the work of the devil, and hasty advice is the work of the Most Merciful" [1]. So, man is after the sun and stars, the animal and plant world. But we humans are the achievement. The World Meteorological Center reports, "Of the 10 worst disasters of the past 50 years, the highest death toll is drought (650,000 deaths)" [2] Now let's think that a large part of the population of the Earth is dying because of the lack of water. we are climbing to the top. According to the private institute of international security problems in Stockholm, there are two main reasons for global hunger: the first is climate o' security, armed conflicts [3]. Let's focus on the first reason. A climate phenomenon is observed on Earth every year. This process entered the list of global problems many years ago. A question arises here. What causes climate itself? Why is this process accelerating year by year? The reason is that man, who is considered a supreme being, could not preserve the wealth given to him. Knowing that nature is an "inexhaustible control", they used it. It did not think that the "endless" would end one day. The whole Earth, on this day, our Motherland, Uzbekistan, is struggling with many problems today. Today, Uzbekistan has become an industrialized, agrarian zone. The development of our country, joining the ranks of the most advanced countries, certainly pleases every citizen of Uzbekistan. But we can also ensure our national ecology in the way of food. There are a number of ecological problems in the Republic of Uzbekistan today, and without finding a solution to them, we cannot preserve our national ecology. They are:

1. Nature conservation problems in the large industrialized Fergana, Navoi, Margilon, Chirchik, Angren, Almalyk and other parks. Here, the social-ecological situation worsens, and the various gases coming out of the industrial centers and the state of the environment are brought to the outside environment.

2. Environmental problems and safety in the agro-industrial complex have not been solved for many years.

3. Contamination of natural waters with pesticides and mineral fertilizers coming from industrial centers.

4. Problems related to cleaning and restoration of flora and fauna, production of resources of national parks.

In our country, production works are being carried out to clean the environment, extract natural resources, improve the national sanitation and ecological situation, and ensure the preservation of the ecosystem. One of them is the law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 30, 2019 "On structures to improve the environment of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". This Concept includes:

- preservation and improvement of the quality of environmental objects (atmospheric objects, water, earth, soil, subsoil, biodiversity, protection of natural resources) from anthropogenic influence and other adverse effects 'to provide;
- upgrading of environmentally safe materials, products, production facilities and other facilities to a higher level;
- getting a strong and stable guard;
- ensuring safe use of toxic and radioactive energy;
- secure provision that can be applied through the associated application;
- the role of controlling the ecological culture of the population and protecting the environment increases the activity of state bodies.

The adoption of such laws and decisions is certainly not without benefit. But it is not possible for the state or responsible persons to protect nature. Every citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan should protect the environment, environmental objects: land, water, soil, atmospheric air and other, and serve the future generations.

The famous scientist Yu.O describes environmental problems in nature as follows: "The production of ecological processes, the maintenance of the environment and its maintenance can be the joint action of the world community and its maintenance." Planet Earth is the common home of mankind. Today, the total population of the earth is 6 billion. From water, air, soil and other resources, which are 6 billion people's natural resources. How many human problems arise because of nature's relationship with nature. Today, modern technologies and safety measures are being used in energy production, production, production of ecologically clean technologies, production of nature, production related to its preservation or ensuring production legislation. Sobriety is the need of the hour. The population of the entire Earth should be indifferent to the environment and the ecological problems related to it, and should be sympathetic to such production issues.

Our ancestors valued every inch of our land and appreciated every drop of water. We young people were also brought up in the spirit of protecting nature. We should also raise our children from childhood to protect nature and its resources, and to criticize the waste that is happening around us.

In conclusion, I can say that we should not ignore the problems related to nature. Let one person plant a tree today. Make more use of water resources or clean up the burning of the autumn season. Over time, the number of these individuals will reach a hundred, from a hundred to a thousand. In this way, all the inhabitants of the Earth get used to this way of life. Conservation of nature begins with the smallest actions. That is, simply turning off the water that flows in vain, and not throwing garbage on the streets, is one of our contributions to the preservation of nature.

References:

1. Nasiruddin Rabguzi. Narrated by Rabguzi.
2. www.kalampir.uz
3. www.zamon.uz
4. www.lex.uz

